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How Brand Awareness Does Not Have a Significant Effect on Customer Loyalty in a Public Company

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Abstract

This article aims to analyze the impact of Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth, Brand Awareness to Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. The research design used in this study is descriptive and verification methods with quantitative approaches. Primary data collected using questionnaires distributed to respondents the form of a statement filled based on Likert scale. Quantitative analysis using structural equation modelling. First, Brand Exposure is included in the good category which means that the strategies prepared for the products sold in order to build brand awareness have been rated well by consumers. In addition, Customer Engagement is included in both categories so that the process of the product to provide opportunities for consumers to engage and interact in two-way communication so as to create an interactive dialogue and provide a personal experience that will be remembered by the customer is said to be good. Second, Electronic Word of Mouth is also included in good categories, which means that product reviews distributed to others by using electronic media according to respondents are considered good. Third, Digital marketing strategies measured by Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth variables each have a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction, where the better the marketing strategy, the Customer Satisfaction on the product will also increase as well as it should. Fourth, Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth each does not have a significant effect on Customer Loyalty. Social Media Marketing Strategy to Customer Loyalty, the response to the evaluation of a product has been said to be good. Customer Loyalty is included in the category of good means the customer remains to re-subscribe or re-buy selected products or services as a consistent attitude in the future has been said to be good. Fifth, Brand Awareness is included in the good category so that the understanding possessed by consumers has the potential to accept the brand and embed it in their minds every time using the product has been said to be good Customer Satisfaction. Sixth, Based on the results of testing the Brand Awareness hypothesis does not have a significant effect on Customer Loyalty, while Customer satisfaction gives a significant positive effect on Customer Loyalty, so the better the Customer Satisfaction, the Customer Loyalty on the product will also increase as well as it should.

Keywords: Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth, Brand Awareness, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty

1. Introduction

Social media has now become a trend in marketing communication. According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), social media is a group of internet-based applications that are built on the ideological and technological framework of Web 2.0 and allow the creation of and content exchange of information from internet users. Web 2.0 is the basis for the formation of social media. Social media is a medium for socializing. Social media uses web-based technology to quickly disseminate large amounts of knowledge and information to internet users. Examples of social media that are developing now are: Twitter, Facebook, MySpace, YouTube, etc.

Media communication has traditionally used the "one to many" model, changing to modern media using the internet (communication on social media) with the "many to many" model. Interactivity can be considered as a co-interaction with "many to many" interactions making social media used by companies to create electronic word of mouth (eWOM). Word of mouth (WOM) is the process of conveying information from person to person and has a major role in making purchasing decisions from consumers (Richins & Root-Shaffer, 1988). In commercial conditions, WOM involves the attitude of consumers in sharing the brand, opinion, or reaction about the business, products, or services of others. Positive WOM is a powerful marketing medium for companies to influence consumers. Along with technological developments, word of mouth is now developing also in social media called the central concept in understanding new media. Electronic word of mouth (eWOM). Although it has the same form as the form of word of mouth, eWOM offers various means of exchanging information, anonymously or in secret. Seeing the rapid development of social media, many companies see this as their opportunity to show their products to the public. So companies must have a superior marketing strategy to be able to attract the attention of the users of social media, especially strategies in the company's marketing communications division. Where the results of previous studies indicate that the role of a company's social media marketing communication influences brand awareness / brand awareness of a company's products by those social media users. Every company has an interest in having good Brand Awareness in front of its customers, strong Brand Awareness indicates that the products of a company are well known to the public and of course this will result in the consistency of consumers to remain loyal to the company's products, in the long run, can be maintained well.

As'ad, Abu Rumman and Alhadid (2014), found that there is a strong relationship between marketing strategies carried out through social media on brand equity, this reflects that social media marketing is very important for a company, especially in telephone provider companies. Research conducted by Bruhn, et.al (2012) divides social media into 2 different types, namely firm-created and user generated. Therefore, in the future there is a possibility that the growth of social media in society will have a stronger influence on functional brand image and hedonic brand image. In the information, it was found that social media negatively influences brand awareness, even though the amount is small. Based on the various explanations above, the researcher is interested in doing research entitled "Analysis of the Effect of Digital Marketing through Social Media on Increasing Brand Awareness, Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty."

The purpose of this study is as follows: To determine the effect of Social Media Marketing Strategies on Brand Awareness. To determine the effect of Social Media Marketing Strategies on Customer Satisfaction. To determine the effect of Social Media Marketing Strategies on Customer Loyalty. To determine the effect of Brand Awareness on Customer Satisfaction. To determine the effect of Brand Awareness and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty.

2. Literature Review

Several studies linking the Analysis of the Effect of Digital Marketing through Social Media on Increasing Brand Awareness, Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty have been conducted by previous researchers and show the findings of various results. Santoso (2012) found that there is an influence between social media on Customer Retention and the dimensions of social media that affect customer retention are media richness and self presentation. This study suggests that increasing customer loyalty leads to increased customer retention, giving rewards, responding to customer complaints quickly, and using traditional media to support

communication between consumers and producers. Sanusi (2015) draw conclusions as follows: Twitter has a number of advantages and uniqueness compared to other social networks, so that with these advantages can be used by companies to maintain and maintain customer loyalty. Admin Twitter Diva Press strives for customer loyalty, by trying to meet the factors that cause customer loyalty. And the factors that cause customer loyalty can be done through Twitter. Good communication by Diva Press delivered via Twitter can have a positive effect on customers. So the company has a great opportunity to continue to maintain customer loyalty as long as it is able to continue to use Twitter and maximize its role. Senjaya et al (2013) found B2C Perspective Growth which is followed by many players in the industry, forces every coffee shop to always try to present the best for its customers. At present the attention is not only focused on the type of food and drink, but also the atmosphere of the coffee shop which is deliberately set as a suitable place for various situations, for example as a place to gather with friends and family, or as a meeting point for business people, even the most important thing right now is the existence of electric sockets because the digital era is unnoticed, making people dependent on electricity, whenever and wherever. Amalina (2016) the results of data analysis have several limitations in this study, so it can be suggested to subsequent researchers as follows: (1) Conducting research outside the independent variable (Social Media Marketing) that affects brand loyalty, considering there is an effect of 76.8% of other variables outside the independent variable (Social Media Marketing) in this study. Such as conducting research to see the effect of product quality, satisfaction, commitment and other factors that can affect brand loyalty. (2) It is difficult to get responses from Mizone followers in answering interviews conducted before providing an online questionnaire link so that it becomes a consideration for future researchers so that questions in the interview can be entered into an online questionnaire as well as to make it easier for researchers to get responses from online questionnaires without going through interviews first first.

Figure 1. Thinking framework

Source: researcher

3. Hypothesis

In Shojae and Azman (2013) explained that brand exposure is a strategy prepared by the company for brands sold in order to build brand awareness. Based on the concept of advertising exposure, consumers who are exposed to advertising, will feel certain feelings and attitudes towards the brand which will then move consumers to buy products. One effect of advertising exposure based on the concept of advertising exposure is that advertising exposure can create brand awareness in the minds of consumers, in addition to that consumers will also know the benefits and the nature of the brand. This study shows that there is a relationship between tagline exposure to brand awareness where the higher exposure to tagline has an impact on the higher brand awareness (Amalina, 2016).

Hypothesis1: Brand Exposure has a significant influence on Product Brand Awareness.

The right brand exposure determined by a company will encourage the formation of good brand awareness as well, the better the brand awareness owned by a company will increase the consumption of consumers / goods or

services produced by the company concerned when the consumer decides to re-repurchase, things this indicates that customer satisfaction has been achieved significantly. In other words the right brand exposure will increase customer satisfaction pretty well too (Senjaya et.al, 2013).

Hypothesis 2: Brand Exposure has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction Products.

Customer engagement has a significant role in shaping the brand awareness or brand awareness of a product in the community, the interactive customer of a product marketed by a company will increase the involvement of the company concerned on the product and ultimately brand awareness will also increase (Santoso, 2012).

Hypothesis 3: Customer Engagement has a significant influence on Product Brand Awareness

Customer involvement is also very important in increasing the level of customer satisfaction of a product, customer involvement will cause a feeling of belonging to the product concerned and will certainly increase the awareness of customers for further product development, where consumers can provide advice, especially if the product can provide satisfaction real for Santoso consumers (2012).

Hypothesis 4: Customer Engagement has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction Products.

The Electronic Word of Mouth process takes place efficiently in cyberspace and social media, people who give positive reactions to a product in social media will be quickly seen and responded to by other social media users, this will certainly make a product easily remembered by the public, which at the end of the brand awareness of the product in question will also increase (Santoso, 2012).

Hypothesis 5: Electronic Word of Mouth has a significant influence on Product Brand Awareness.

The right Electronic Word of Mouth process through social media will help in providing the right information related to the product being marketed, so that every satisfaction or complaint handling of a product will be very easy to share information with users of social media, so that customer satisfaction can be maintained consistently (Senjaya, et.al 2013).

Hypothesis 6: Electronic Word of Mouth gives a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction Products.

Brand awareness consists of brand recognition and brand recall performance. Brand recognition is the competence of customers who identify the brand as one, which was previously exposed. Product promotion through brand awareness is one of the easiest and most effective ways to promote commodity related products because they have relatively few differences, which makes it increasingly difficult for their companies to differentiate their brands as long as they do not have strong brands. Customers tend to make decisions quickly about a product if they know or recognize the brand. The better the consumer can identify, remember and remember the company's brand. Because of the trust they have in their brand, it contributes to the level of customer satisfaction (Senjaya et.al, 2013).

Hypothesis 7: Brand Awareness has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction Products.

Brand awareness shows the ability of prospective buyers to recognize or recall that a brand is part of a particular brand category. The role of brand awareness in overall brand equity depends on the level of awareness achieved by a brand. Brand awareness will encourage customer loyalty to the products produced by a company. The role of brand awareness in overall brand equity depends on the level of awareness achieved by a brand. Brand awareness is built by giving a good name and in that name contains a very high meaning and value, where awareness of the brand is built so well continuously throughout the life cycle of the product. Brand awareness is celebrated and heightened through the recognition of a deep brand, the culmination of results when consumers have deep experience of the brand. Consumers who have enough experience of a brand through what they see, hear or even know, the brand will be directly in the memory. Thus, consumers who have brand awareness of the product will tend to choose the product and are loyal so that it can be said that brand awareness is related to customer loyalty (Amalina, 2016).

Hypothesis 8: Brand Awareness has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty Products.

In the research conducted, it was found that customer satisfaction has a positive effect on customer loyalty. (Senjaya et.al, 2013).

Hypothesis 9: Customer Satisfaction has a significant influence on Customer Loyalty Products.

4. Research Methods

Thus, the subject in this study is, with the unit of analysis which is interpreted as something related to the focus / component under study, namely consumers. Descriptive method in this research is used to describe the research objects used, among others, is to find out the description of marketing strategies through social media consisting of Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, and Electronic Word of Mouth, Brand Awareness, Customer satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. In this verification method research is used in accordance with research objectives relating to the Social Media Marketing Strategy for Brand Awareness, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty, the effect of Brand Awareness on Customer Satisfaction in as well as the influence of Brand Awareness and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty. In accordance with the objectives of the study as well as the unit of analysis in the study, the population in this study was all consumers, but given the large number of consumers the total population in this study could not be known with certainty and then determined the number of samples where each consumers do not have the same opportunity to be used as research samples and will be determined the number of samples or sample size based on sampling techniques. Especially for the Structural Equation Model (SEM), the determination of the number of samples has its own rules that are different from the determination of the number of samples commonly used in ordinary statistical research. This study has a sample range of 100 - 300. So it can be concluded that the recommendations in this study are the sample size of the data to be used as many as 200 samples. Slovin formula is one of the simple and easy ways to calculate the number of samples. Primary data used in this study are data collected by researchers based on a questionnaire distributed to respondents in this case the consumer is a statement filled in based on the choice of answers provided. The type of questionnaire used was a questionnaire containing statements accompanied by alternative answers that have been provided relating to marketing strategies through social media consisting of Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, and Electronic Word of Mouth, Brand Awareness, Customer satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty.

The scale used in this research instrument is the Likert scale. By using a Likert scale, each answer is associated with a positive or negative statement. The answer scale provisions are as follows: Strongly Agree: 5, Agree: 4, Quite Agree: 3, Disagree: 2, Strongly disagree: 1. Then to produce a good instrument, it is necessary to test the research instrument, namely the validity and reliability tests. Validity illustrates how the questionnaire is really capable of measuring what will be measured. So it can be said that the higher the validity of a test, the more accurate the test kit is about its target. Since it is never recommended to carry out a significant test on item analysis, the technique used is total item correlation, that is consistency between item items as a whole, which is the basis of person (product moment) correlation. Because in reality it is difficult to find a validity coefficient greater than 0.60, then the validity coefficient between 0.30 - 0.40 is considered high enough to be used in a study. Based on the calculation results, it can be seen that the validity index value of each statement item is greater than the critical value of 0.3 thus it can be concluded that all statement items on all three variables are valid and fit to be used as a measurement tool for Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth variables, Brand Awareness, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty.

Reliability relates to the degree of consistency and stability of data or findings. In a quantitative view, a data is declared reliable if two or more researchers in the same object produce the same data, or a group of data when broken into two shows different data. The reliability calculation technique used in this study is the Cronbach's Alpha test. The scale reliability coefficient must be tried as high as possible, the magnitude of which is close to one. The decision rule uses the alpha Cronbach critical value, namely if the coefficient value ≥ 0.70 , then the instrument is declared reliable and can be used for research. The reliability value of the statement items on the questionnaire of the three variables being studied is greater than 0.70. These results indicate that the questionnaire items on the four variables namely Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth, Brand Awareness, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty are reliable. Descriptive analysis is intended to get an overview / description of the responses of respondents regarding Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth, Brand Awareness, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty. After the test, the next step the researcher conducts a quantitative analysis assessment as a phenomenal picture of the

current research variables. To find out how the conditions and the level of suitability of each of these variables, the researcher makes categorization in the interval line as follows: The total number of respondents is 200 people and for the largest measurement scale value is 5 while the smallest measurement scale value is 1. b. Obtained an average ideal score is $5 \times 200 = 1000$ and the average smallest score is $1 \times 200 = 200$. The smallest percentage value is $(200: 1000) \times 100\% = 20\%$. Obtained range value of $100\% - 20\% = 80\%$ if divided by 5 measurement scales will get a percentage interval value of 16%, then the category of score interpretation: **Score:** 20% to 36%, **Category:** Very poor/low. >36% to 52%: Not good/low >52% to 68%: Sufficient/moderate >68% to 84%. Good/high: >84% to 99%. Very good/ very high: >99%

4.1 Structural Equation Modeling Analysis (SEM)

A complete SEM modeling basically consists of the Measurement Model and the Structural Model. The measurement model is intended to confirm the dimensions developed on a factor. Structural Model is a model regarding the structure of relationships that form or explain causality between factors. Structural Equations. While the independent variables are all constructs that have lines with arrows connecting to endogenous constructs. This equation is basically built with the following guidelines: Endogenous Variables = Exogenous Variables + Endogenous Variables + Error. Where researchers determine the variables that measure constructs and determine a series of matrices that indicate conditions hypothesized between constructs or variables.

4.2 Conformity Test and Statistical Test

A model is declared feasible if each of these indexes has a cut of value as shown in Table 3.5 below:

Table 1. Goodness of-fit Index

No	Goodness of-fit index	Cut-off Value
1	Chi-square	< chi square Table
2	Significance Probability	≥ 0.05
3	RMSEA	≤ 0.08
4	GFI	≥ 0.90
5	AGFI	≥ 0.90
6	CMIN/DF	≤ 2.00
7	TLI	≥ 0.95
8	CFI	≥ 0.95

Source: Developed for this research

4.3 Interpretation and modification the model

The final step in SEM is to interpret and modify the model, especially for models that do not meet the requirements in the testing process. After the model is estimated, the residual must be small or close to zero and the frequency distribution of the residual covariance must be symmetric. Modification of the model is first tested by testing the standardized residual carried out by the model. A cut-off value of 2.58 can be used to assess the significance of the residuals generated by the model. A residual value greater than or equal to 2.58 is interpreted as being statically significant at the 5% level, and this significant residual indicates a substantial prediction error for a pair of indicators.

4.4 Hypothesis test

In conducting hypothesis testing about causality there are two hypotheses, namely: H_0 . The null hypothesis states that the regression coefficient between relationships is equal to zero through the t test which is commonly used in regression models. H_1 . Alternative hypotheses can be used with two things, namely: The level of significance

or probability (α), namely the probability of making a type I error, namely the error rejecting the hypothesis when the hypothesis is true. The significance level that is commonly used is 0.05 with the level of significance ranging from 0.01 to 0.1. The relationship between variables with a significance level above 0.05 indicates that the relationship is a significant relationship. The level of confidence, which is the level at which 95% of the sample value will represent the value of the population from which the sample originated.

5. RESEARCH RESULT

The number of respondents based on the age of the respondent. The majority 126 respondents 15 years old. Majority of 116 respondents or 58% are respondents with female gender.

5.1 Descriptive analysis.

5.1.1. Respondents' Responses Regarding Brand Exposure

Brand Exposure is measured by 12 item statements with 6 dimensions, namely simple, unexpected, persuasive, relevant, entertaining, and acceptable. In the Brand Exposure variable with 12 item statement items and 200 respondents, a total score of 8793 was obtained and a percentage of 73.28%, so that the total score of respondents' responses to the 12 statement items regarding Brand Exposure was included in both categories.

5.1.2. Respondents' Responses Regarding Customer Engagement

Customer Engagement is measured by 7 statement items with 3 dimensions, namely the physical, cognitive, emotional presence of the customer, the intensity of customer participation and activity, and interactive experiences between customers and the company. In the Customer Engagement variable with 7 item statement items and 200 respondents, a total score of 5114 and a percentage of 73.06% was obtained, so that from the total score of respondents' responses to the 7 statement items regarding Customer Engagement are included in both categories.

5.1.3. Respondents' Responses Regarding Electronic Word of Mouth

Electronic Word of Mouth is measured by 4 item statements with 3 dimensions, namely concern for others, express positive feeling, and helping the company. In the Electronic Word of Mouth variable with the number of items statement 4 items and the number of respondents 200 people, obtained a total score of 2174 and a percentage of 72.75%, so from the total score of respondents' responses to 4 items submitted regarding Electronic Word of Mouth are included in both categories.

5.1.4. Respondents' Responses Regarding Brand Awareness

Brand Awareness is measured by 4 items statement with 3 dimensions, namely brands that are often remembered, known and referred to. On the Brand Awareness variable with the number of items statement 6 items and the number of respondents 200 people, obtained a total score of 4397 and a percentage of 73.28%, so that from the total score of respondents' responses to the 6 items submitted regarding Brand Awareness included in both categories.

5.1.5. Respondents Response Regarding Customer Satisfaction

Customer Satisfaction is measured by 3 item statements with 3 dimensions, namely re-purchase, word of mouth, and brand image. In the Customer Satisfaction variable with 3 item statement items and 200 respondents, a total score of 2188 was obtained and a percentage of 76.90%, so that from the total score of respondent responses to 3 item statements submitted regarding Customer Satisfaction included in both categories.

5.1.6. Respondents' Responses Regarding Customer Loyalty

Customer Loyalty is measured by 6 statement items with 3 dimensions: service reuse, positively embedded service in the minds of customers, and always the first choice. In the Customer Loyalty variable with the number of items statement 6 items and the number of respondents 200 people, obtained a total score of 4373 and a percentage of 72.88%, so that from the total score of respondents' responses to the 6 items submitted statements regarding Customer Loyalty included in either category.

5.2 Quantitative Analysis

Assumptions that must be fulfilled in data collection and processing procedures that are analyzed by SEM modeling. Testing is done by looking at the results of standardized regression weight in the output table. If there is an estimate value of the indicators that have a significance level ≤ 0.50 then the indicator cannot describe the construct. Model compatibility (goodness of fit), for confirmatory factor analysis will also be tested. Furthermore, conclusions on the suitability of the model built will be seen from the results of the goodness of fit measurements obtained. The goodness of fit test is first performed on the confirmatory factor analysis model. The following is a form of goodness of fit analysis.

Table 2. Loading Factor Coefficient Value for Each Indicator for Brand Exposure Constructions

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
x16 <--- Brand_Exposure	1.000				
x15 <--- Brand_Exposure	.847	.108	7.872	***	par_1
x14 <--- Brand_Exposure	3.230	.306	10.538	***	par_2
x13 <--- Brand_Exposure	2.194	.215	10.220	***	par_3
x12 <--- Brand_Exposure	1.989	.211	9.433	***	par_4
x11 <--- Brand_Exposure	3.061	.290	10.564	***	par_5
x23 <--- Customer_Engagement	1.000				
x22 <--- Customer_Engagement	1.063	.100	10.624	***	par_1
x21 <--- Customer_Engagement	1.486	.138	10.753	***	par_2
x33 <--- EWOM	1.000				
x32 <--- EWOM	1.065	.152	7.000	***	par_1
x31 <--- EWOM	3.059	.516	5.926	***	par_2
y13 <--- Brand_Awareness	1.000				
y12 <--- Brand_Awareness	.879	.075	11.704	***	par_1
y11 <--- Brand_Awareness	.817	.070	11.691	***	par_2
y23 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	1.000				
y22 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	.941	.163	5.786	***	par_1
y21 <--- Customer_Satisfaction	.943	.164	5.755	***	par_2
z13 <--- Customer_Loyalty	1.000				
z12 <--- Customer_Loyalty	.966	.090	10.731	***	par_1
z11 <--- Customer_Loyalty	.903	.085	10.661	***	par_2

Source: processed data

The confirmatory factor analysis phase of the Brand Exposure construct aims to test the unidimensionality of the dimensions forming each latent variable. These latent variables or Brand Exposure constants consist of 1 unobserved variable with 6 observed variables as their constituents. The table shows that the p value for the six construct indicators for the Brand Exposure is in accordance with the required p value which is $p < 0.05$. This means that the six indicators are declared valid and can form the Brand Exposure construct.

The confirmatory factor analysis phase of the Customer Engagement construct aims to test the unidimensionality of the dimensions forming each latent variable. These latent variables or Customer Engagement constants consist of 1 unobserved variable with 3 observed variables as its constituents. The table shows that the p value for the three indicators of the Customer Engagement construct is in accordance with the required p value which is $p < 0.05$. This means that the Customer Engagement indicator is declared valid and can form the Customer Engagement construct. The confirmatory factor analysis phase of the Electronic Word of Mouth construct aims to test the unidimensionality of the dimensions forming each latent variable. These latent variables or Electronic Word of Mouth constants consist of 1 unobserved variable with 3 observed variables as its constituents. The table shows that the p value for the three construct indicators of the Electronic Word of Mouth is in accordance

with the required p value of $p < 0.05$. This means that the Electronic Word of Mouth indicator is declared valid and can form the construct of the Electronic Word of Mouth.

The confirmatory factor analysis phase of the Brand Awareness construct aims to test the unidimensionality of the dimensions forming each latent variable. These latent variables or Brand Awareness constants consist of 1 unobserved variable with 3 observed variables as their constituents. The table shows that the p value for the three construct indicators for Brand Awareness is in accordance with the required p value, which is $p < 0.05$. This means that the Brand Awareness indicator is declared valid and can form the Brand Awareness construct.

The confirmatory factor analysis phase of the Customer Satisfaction construct aims to test the unidimensionality of the dimensions forming each latent variable. These latent variables or the Customer Satisfaction construct consist of 1 unobserved variable with 3 observed variables as their constituents indicating that the p value for the three indicators of the Customer Satisfaction construct is in accordance with the required p value ie $p < 0.05$. This means that the Customer Satisfaction indicator is declared valid and can form the construct of Customer Satisfaction.

The confirmatory factor analysis phase of the Customer Loyalty construct aims to test the unidimensionality of the dimensions forming each latent variable. These latent variables or Customer Loyalty constants consist of 1 unobserved variable with 3 observed variables as its constituents. The table shows that the p-value for the three indicators of the Customer Loyalty construct is in accordance with the required p-value i.e. $p < 0.05$. This means that the Customer Loyalty indicator is declared valid and can form the Customer Loyalty construct. The next analysis is the Full Model Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis which is intended to test the models and hypotheses developed in this study. Testing the model in the Structural Equation Model is done with two tests, namely the suitability of the model test and the test of the significance of causality through the regression coefficient test. Furthermore, the test results can be seen in below:

Figure 2 Structural Equation Model Analysis

Source: AMOS

Table 3. Evaluation of Goodness of Fit Criteria in Structural Equation Model

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut Off Value	Results	Explanation
Chi Square (χ^2)	χ^2 tabel	191,622	Good
Significant Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0.084	Good

GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.990	Good
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0.886	Marginal
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	1.154	Good
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0.987	Good
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0.028	Good
CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0.990	Good

Source: processed data

Based on table above, it can be seen that the structural model that has been modified has fulfilled the cut-off value quite well. Thus it can be concluded that the model has been said to be good and acceptable.

5.3 Hypothesis test

Testing hypothesis done by analyzing the value of C.R (Critical Ratio) and the value of P value then compared with the statistical limits that have been required, namely above 2.0 for CR values and below 0.05 for P values. If the results of data processing indicate a value that meets these requirements, the proposed research hypothesis can be accepted. Furthermore, discussion on hypothesis testing will be carried out in stages in accordance with the order of the hypothesis that has been proposed.

The value of the regression weight coefficient between the Brand Exposure variable for Brand Awareness is 1,374 with a probability of 0,000 or $p < 0.05$ and has a critical ratio (C.R) of 5.734 or more than 1.96 then H_0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence between Brand Exposure on Brand Awareness.

The value of the regression weight coefficient between the Brand Exposure variable to Customer Satisfaction is 0.338 with a probability of 0.037 or $p < 0.05$ and has a critical ratio (C.R) of 2.081 or more than 1.96 then H_0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence between Brand Exposure on Customer Satisfaction.

The value of the regression weight coefficient between the variable Customer Engagement to Brand Awareness is 0.220 with a probability of 0.007 or $p < 0.05$ and has a critical ratio (C.R) of 2.705 or more than 1.96 then H_0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence between Customer Engagement on Brand Awareness.

The value of the regression weight coefficient between Customer Engagement variables and Customer Satisfaction is 0.286 with a probability of 0.031 or $p < 0.05$ and has a critical ratio (C.R) of 2.159 or more than 1.96 then H_0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence between Customer Engagement on Customer Satisfaction.

Standardized regression weight coefficient between Electronic Word of Mouth variables and Brand Awareness with a probability of 0.04 or $p < 0.05$ and having a critical ratio (C.R) of 2.057 or more than 1.96, H_0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence between Electronic Word of Mouth on Brand Awareness.

The value of the regression weight coefficient between Electronic Word of Mouth variables to Customer Satisfaction is 0.085 with a probability of 0.013 or $p < 0.05$ and has a critical ratio (C.R) of 2.368 or more than 1.96 then H_0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence between Electronic Word of Mouth on Customer Satisfaction.

The value of the regression weight coefficient between the Brand Awareness variable to Customer Satisfaction is 0.387 with a probability of 0.406 or $p > 0.05$ and has a critical ratio (C.R) of -0.831 or smaller than 1.96 then H_0 is accepted. This means there is no significant effect between Brand Awareness on Customer Satisfaction.

The value of the regression weight coefficient between the Customer Satisfaction variable against the Customer Loyalty is 2,826 with a probability of 0.049 or $p < 0.05$ and has a critical ratio (C.R) of 2.441 or more than 1.96

then H_0 is rejected. This means that there is a significant influence between Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty.

Based on the results of the analysis obtained shows that there are several hypotheses that $H_1 - H_6$ were accepted, others rejected.

5.4 Analysis of Direct Effects, Indirect Effects, and Total Effects

The magnitude of the effect of each latent variable directly (Standardized direct effect) or indirectly (Standardized indirect effect) and the total effect (Standardized total effect). The magnitude of the influence of each latent variable directly effect and indirect effect and the total effect is explained as follows:

1. Brand Exposure gives a direct influence on Brand Awareness 0.974.
2. Brand Exposure has a direct effect on Customer Satisfaction of 1,556 with an indirect effect of -0,614 and a total influence 0.944.
3. Customer Engagement gives a direct influence on Brand Awareness 0.324.
4. Customer Engagement has a direct effect on Customer Satisfaction of 0.685 with an indirect effect of -0.614 and a total influence 0.480.
5. Electronic Word of Mouth provides a direct influence on Brand Awareness 0.244
6. Electronic Word of Mouth gives a direct influence on Customer Satisfaction of 0.1 with an indirect effect of -0.154 and a total effect -0.053.
7. Brand Awareness has a direct influence on Customer Satisfaction -0,630.
8. Brand Awareness gives a direct influence on Customer Loyalty of 1.272 with an indirect effect of -1.027 and a total effect of 0.245.
9. Customer Satisfaction gives a direct influence on Customer Loyalty of 1,630.

5.5 Discussion of Research Results with Previous Research

The results of research conducted by As'ad and Alhadid (2014), there is a strong relationship between marketing strategies carried out through social media on brand equity, this reflects that social media marketing is very important for a company. The results of the hypothesis testing of this study which there is a significant influence between Brand Exposure and Brand Awareness. Research conducted by Bruhn, et.al (2012) divides social media into 2 different types, namely firm-created and user generated. Therefore, in the future there is a possibility that the growth of social media in society will have a stronger influence on functional brand image and hedonic brand image. This is different from the results of the hypothesis test conducted in this study.

6. CONCLUSION

1. Brand Exposure is included in the good category which means that the strategies prepared for the products sold in order to build brand awareness have been rated well by consumers. In addition, Customer Engagement is included in both categories so that the process of the product to provide opportunities for consumers to engage and interact in two-way communication so as to create an interactive dialogue and provide a personal experience that will be remembered by the customer is said to be good.
2. Electronic Word of Mouth is also included in good categories, which means that product reviews distributed to others by using electronic media according to respondents are considered good.
3. Digital marketing strategies measured by Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth variables each have a significant positive effect on Customer Satisfaction, where the better the marketing strategy, the Customer Satisfaction on the product will also increase as well as it should.
4. Brand Exposure, Customer Engagement, Electronic Word of Mouth each does not have a significant effect on Customer Loyalty. Social Media Marketing Strategy to Customer Loyalty, the response to the evaluation of a product has been said to be good. Customer Loyalty is included in the category of good means the customer remains to re-subscribe or re-buy selected products or services as a consistent attitude in the future has been said to be good.

5. Brand Awareness is included in the good category so that the understanding possessed by consumers has the potential to accept the brand and embed it in their minds every time using the product has been said to be good. Customer Satisfaction
6. Based on the results of testing the Brand Awareness hypothesis does not have a significant effect on Customer Loyalty, while Customer satisfaction gives a significant positive effect on Customer Loyalty, so the better the Customer Satisfaction, the Customer Loyalty on the product will also increase as well as it should.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the results of research and conclusions that have been presented, will propose suggestions in the hope that it will benefit all interested parties.

1. Respondents responses to brand exposure is based on the percentage of the total score of respondents' responses it can be seen that the respondent's responses to the 12 statements submitted regarding Brand Exposure are included in both categories. Then this variable can be ascertained biased run in the implementation of corporate strategy.
2. Respondents responses regarding customer engagement, which is based on the percentage of the total score of respondents' responses, it can be seen that respondents' responses to 7 items submitted regarding Customer Engagement are included in both categories. Therefore this variable can be implemented well in the future.
3. Respondents responses to the Electronic word of mouth strategy Based on the percentage of the total score of the respondents' responses it can be seen that the respondents' responses to the 4 items submitted regarding Electronic Word of Mouth are included in both categories. Product reviews that are distributed to others in electronic media are said to be good.
4. Respondents responses regarding brand awareness, which is based on the percentage of the total score of respondents' responses, it can be seen that the respondents' responses to 6 items submitted regarding Brand Awareness are included in both categories. This variable will be very effective if it is run by a company.
5. Respondents responses regarding Customer Satisfaction, based on the percentage of the total score of the respondents' responses it can be seen that the respondent's responses to the 3 item statements submitted regarding Customer Satisfaction are included in both categories. Product customer satisfaction needs to be maintained and continuously improved because customer satisfaction will have an impact on customer loyalty.
6. Respondents responses regarding Customer loyalty, which is based on the percentage of the total score of respondents' responses, it can be seen that the respondents' responses to 6 items submitted regarding Customer Loyalty are included in both categories. Customers persist in re-subscribing or re-buying selected products or services as a consistent attitude in the future is already said to be good.] (Garamond 12)

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